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D2.3 Datasets and policies data models

(Version 1.2, 05/12/2022)

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	5
List of Figures	5
List of Tables	5
Abbreviations	7
Executive summary	8
1 Introduction	9
1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy project	9
1.2 Description of WP2 “Specifications and co-creation for AI-based policy management”	9
1.3 Purpose and scope	9
1.4 Structure of the deliverable	10
1.5 Relation to other WPs and tasks	10
2 Methodology	12
3 Pilots Data Sources	13
3.1 Management and Optimization of City Resources (DAEM)	13
3.2 Energy Management Policies Pilot (LIS)	15
3.3 Citizens and Businesses Services Optimization (CDG)	35
3.4 Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance Policies (BURGAS)	43
3.5 Holistic and Accessible Urban Mobility (NIC)	45
4 Dataset Model Design	52
5 Policy Model Design	54
5.1 Policy	54
5.2 AI Model	55
6 Conclusions	55
Annexes	56
Annex 1: Template for collecting data sources from Pilots	56

List of Figures

Figure 1: AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach	11
Figure 2: AI4PublicPolicy Data Model	53
Figure 3: AI4PublicPolicy Policy Model	54
Figure 4: AI4PublicPolicy AI Model	55

List of Tables

Table 1: Incident management reports	13
Table 2: Incident management reports of activity history	13
Table 3: Wallet transactions	14
Table 4: Parking transactions	14

Table 5: City Sensors Locations.....	15
Table 6: City Sensors Last Record.....	16
Table 7: City Sensors Historical data	17
Table 8: Gree Structure.....	19
Table 9: Cycling Network	19
Table 10: Roads Network – main	20
Table 11: Roads Network – secondary	21
Table 12: Buildings & Demographics	22
Table 13: Meteo Reference Stations.....	27
Table 14: Meteo Reference Stations.....	28
Table 15: Meteo forecast	28
Table 16: Weather class	29
Table 17: Rainfall Class	30
Table 18: Wind Class.....	30
Table 19: Buildings Registry	31
Table 20: Buildings data.....	31
Table 21: Renewable Energy Systems (RES) Systems	32
Table 22: Solar Radiation (hourly).....	33
Table 23: Solar Radiation (yearly).....	33
Table 24: Digital Surface Model (DSM)	34
Table 25: Slope and Orientation.....	34
Table 26: Building Footprint EC	34
Table 27: Energy consumption.....	35
Table 28: Accidents	35
Table 29: Meteo data	37
Table 30: AMT Stops	39
Table 31: Post.....	40
Table 32: Category	40
Table 33: User	41
Table 34: Group.....	41
Table 35: Type.....	42
Table 36: Facility Management Database	42
Table 37: Measurement Location.....	43
Table 38: Smart Pipes	43
Table 39: Accidents, Metered Water and Water Losses.....	44
Table 40: Measurements	44
Table 41: Nicosia Buses - Calendar CPT	45
Table 42: Nicosia Buses - TRIPS CPT	46
Table 43: Nicosia Buses - STOPS CPT	46
Table 44: Nicosia Buses ROUTES – CPT.....	47
Table 45: Smart Parking Management.....	48
Table 46: Monitoring Environmental.....	49
Table 47: Traffic Analysis.....	49
Table 48: SPL Sensor.....	50
Table 49: Patrol Reports	52

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HPC	High Performance Computing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document (D2.3 “Datasets and policies data models V1”) was developed within the framework of regarding the specifications of the AI technologies and VPME of the project. WP2 “Specifications and Co-Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”. WP2 is devoted to producing key specifications for the project’s AI-based policy making paradigm, while including the user studies and the co-creation activities. The WP2 user studies and co-creation sessions will provide requirements for integrating and operating the pilot systems, while at the same time receiving feedback from the pilot systems

This document delivers the specification of the data models that will drive the overall policy management process. In particular, the task has the objective of highlighting the specific characteristics of the logical schema of the provided datasets and policies.

With regard to the Datasets, an extended questionnaire was circulated to all partners developing pilots, to gather all the possible information on the available data sources. This process was vital to identify best practices and scenarios regarding domain models and to analyse the data sources in order to define the data models that will be used in the AI4PublicPolicy platform to feed the AI algorithms. The outcomes of the algorithms are then used as input for the tools developed in the WP5.

With regard to the Policies an analytical model was designed as a structural representation that will be used to define the Policy and collect and evaluate the outcomes of the AI Tools through the AI-Based Policy Making Process.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI's potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens' participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project's AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project's developments. AI4PublicPolicy's business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e. public authorities and other policy makers) around the project's platform.

1.2 Description of WP2 “Specifications and co-creation for AI-based policy management”

The objectives of WP2 are to:

- Specify the overall architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform by identifying components, their functionalities and interconnection, ensuring their coherency with the requirements and global architecture.
- Identify and track end user and technical requirements provided by the use case partners and the technical contributors of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Review the standards and regulations and identify appropriate ones that need to be monitored and followed in the project.
- Analyse the policy making processes to ensure that the outcomes of the project address and enhance/improve these processes, while reducing the bottlenecks in public administration and ensuring high quality and adoption of results.
- Define the data models of the datasets and the policy models to be utilized for the development, training and actual utilization of the AI models and algorithms of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Define the co-creation. Relevant activities will be regularly reported in D2.8, in-line with the description of the deliverable.

1.3 Purpose and scope

AI4PublicPolicy is a data-driven project. So, understanding the data for every pilot and building correct data models are crucial for the success of the project. Each pilot will have their own domain terminology and the datasets will contain the corresponding data.

The goal of this document is to:

- Analyse datasets received from different pilots and find common themes and use them to build data models that could be used across all pilots.

- For datasets that are relevant only for specific domains, build data models that will be used exclusively for those domains.
- Specify the analytical model of the AI-Based Policy, as structural representations that will be enriched through the outcomes of the AI algorithms towards data-driven policy making

Datasets could be coming from diverse data sources (public administration datasets, open datasets, social media, content generated by local actors etc.).

It is expected that this document will be refined in the next revisions to incorporate new data.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

D2.3 “Datasets and policies data models V1” involves five chapters that discuss and analyse in detail the data sources that will be used to define the data models and describe the base structure of the latter.

More specifically:

- The **first chapter** of the document provides an introductory text describing the objectives of this deliverable, a brief description of WP2 “Specifications and Co-Creation for AI-Based Policy Management”, the purpose and scope of the deliverable, its structure and relation to other WPs and tasks.
- The **second chapter** of the deliverable provides the general methodology that was implemented and presented to the various pilots in order to obtain the required information at this phase of the project.
- The **third chapter** describes the AI4PublicPolicy pilot data sources, the process for collecting the data and the specific attributes and characteristics of the domain datasets.
- The **fourth chapter** of the document analyses the pilot data sources in order to define the data model that will be utilized from the AI algorithms developed in AI4PublicPolicy.
- The **fifth chapter** of the document provide the analytical model of the AI-Based Policy, as a structural representation that will be enriched through the outcomes of the AI Tools.

Finally, the document includes a **sixth chapter** with the conclusions of the document, as well as a section with useful **appendices** related to the document.

1.5 Relation to other WPs and tasks

WP2 “Specifications and co-creation for AI-based policy management” is devoted to producing key specifications for the project’s AI-based policy making paradigm, while including the user studies and the co-creation activities. More specifically, this work package:

- interacts horizontally with WP1 that includes all the project management activities of AI4PublicPolicy and monitors all the work packages.
- drives all the technical development work packages of the project (i.e., WP3, WP4, WP5, WP7) through providing technical specifications and the AI4PublicPolicy platform architecture.
- has a two-way interaction with the pilot tasks of WP6; on the one hand, the WP2 user studies and co-creation session will provide requirements for integrating and operating the pilot systems, while at the same time receiving feedback from the pilot systems regarding the specifications of the AI technologies and VPME of the project.
- feeds WP8 with useful content to disseminate regarding the advances of the pilots and the outcomes of the co-creation activities of the project.

Hence, WP2 interacts with all the other WPs of the project by providing specifications, requirements and feedback on both a technical and implementational level.

Figure 1: AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

This document defines datasets that are used as an input to AI algorithms (WP4 and WP5 packages). The policy model is an output of AI algorithms.

The output of this document (data models) is used in the T3.2 (Ontologies and Archetypes for Semantic Interoperability). That means that the data models should be built with the interoperability between different pilots in mind – similar entities from different domains should be unified.

2 Methodology

In this chapter the methodology used to define the available data sources will be described, this also involves the process designed to collect and analyse the data needed to build the policy models.

Regarding the collection of the data from the data sources that the pilot applications are currently using, this was part of a common methodology proposed by the project management board regarding how to address the pilot cases and the responsible partners in order to gather all required information.

To start, an extended excel questionnaire was circulated to all technical facilitators of the pilots in order to retrieve information regarding the specification of the involved datasets, with additional details about the data fields and their typology. This questionnaire has been uploaded in the private document repository of the project. Each of the pilots has provided information about all datasets that are planning to exploit during the project, with the information being requested per dataset presented below:

Description:	A brief description of the data set, its usage and collection mechanisms
Format:	CSV, TSV, JSON, XML, JPG, MP3, etc
Protocol:	The protocol used to access the data (FTP, File sharing, Web service)
Protocol details:	Endpoints, credentials, etc
Sample:	Put a link to a file with a sample of the data source (e.g. a JSON file, a CSV file etc). The sample should follow the same format that will be used during data exchange.
Access restrictions:	Proprietary or Open Data or other access restrictions
Volume:	Size of the dataset in number of records or GBs
Historical data:	The period of historical data in months
Anonymization:	Have you applied any kind of anonymization of the provided data?
Security and Privacy Considerations:	State here if the data processors should be aware of any security and privacy considerations. Should we treat the data as confidential?

Of particular importance are the information regarding the security and anonymization of the data provided, also for the possible implications regarding the GDPR and their future use as input for the AI algorithms developed.

Furthermore, task T2.3 has also required a definition of the data model to be used to feed the AI algorithms of the AI4PublicPolicy platform. Starting with the data collected from the data sources evaluated above, a single UML model was built, where the common data among the different datasets were organized into common entities and the specific data of each domain were kept in their original structures. The relational types between the different entities were identified and consequently a connection between the different domains was made available.

Another important part was defining policy models that will also be utilized for the Policy development along with dataset models. Following the CRISP-DM methodology and considering the Policy as an AI problem, we designed the Policy Model as a set of attributes and related entities that represents:

- Problem understanding
- Data understanding
- AI modelling
- AI outcomes

3 Pilots Data Sources

Each pilot provided the data related to his domain, to begin designing the structure of the data model to be used as input for the AI4PublicPolicy tools. The collected data are presented below divided by pilot with a description of the type of fields received.

3.1 Management and Optimization of City Resources (DAEM)

Table 1: Incident management reports

Description	This dataset contains all the incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution,	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, web service	
Protocol details	HTTP API to be developed, file exports available on demand	
Sample	Incident management reports sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	100k records	
Historical data	3 years	
Anonymization	Fully anonymized data	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
ID	The report ID	Number
Creation date	The creation date of the incident report	Datetime
Issue	The issue type	Text
Address	The location address of the incident report	Text
Description	The description of the report	Text
Authority Service	The authority services to which the report has been assigned.	List of strings
Progress status	The progress status of the report	String
Location longitude	The longitude of the report location	Coordinates
Location latitude	The latitude of the report location	Coordinates
Completion date	The date on which the reported issue have been resolved	Datetime
Due date	The date on which the reported issue is due for resolution	Datetime

Table 2: Incident management reports of activity history

Description	This dataset contains all the activity history of incidents that are reported by citizens in the city of Athens and are sent to the authority for resolution,	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, web service	
Protocol details	HTTP API to be developed, file exports available on demand	
Sample	Incident management reports activity history sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	~300k records	
Historical data	3 years	

Anonymization	Fully anonymized data	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
ID	The report ID	Link to Incident Management reports record
Activity date	The date on which the new activity on the linked report has been recorded	Datetime
Activity type	The type of the incident report activity	Text

Table 3: Wallet transactions

Description	This dataset contains all the transactions that the citizens or visitors execute with their digital wallet for parking services	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, web service	
Protocol details	HTTP API to be developed, file exports available on demand	
Sample	Wallet transactions sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	~500k records	
Historical data	30 months	
Anonymization	Fully anonymized data	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Creation date	The transaction creation date	Datetime
Type	The transaction type	String, one of (Topup, Refund,)
Service type	The service to which this transaction is linked to	String (typically Parking)
Amount	The transaction amount	Amount in Euros
Success status	The status of the transaction	Yes=Successful, No=Failed

Table 4: Parking transactions

Description	This dataset contains all the purchases/activations that the citizens or visitors execute for parking tickets	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, web service	
Protocol details	HTTP API to be developed, file exports available on demand	
Sample	Parking transactions sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	~300k records	
Historical data	30 months	
Anonymization	Fully anonymized data	

Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Creation date	The transaction creation date	Datetime
Type	The transaction type	String, typically Purchase
Service type	The service to which this transaction is linked to	String (typically Parking)
Amount	The purchase amount	Amount in Euros
Success status	The status of the transaction	String, Yes=Successful, No=Failed
Start parking at	The date and time the purchased parking ticket/session starts	Datetime
End parking at	The date and time the purchased parking ticket/session ends	Datetime
Parking duration	The duration of the purchased parking ticket/session	Number in minutes
Cancel parking at	The date and time the purchased parking ticket/session has been cancelled	Datetime, present only if the ticket has been cancelled
Parking location address	The address of the parking location	Text
Parking zone	The parking zone	Text
Extension status	The extension status of the parking ticket	String, Yes=The ticket has been extended, No=the ticket is not extended

3.2 Energy Management Policies Pilot (LIS)

Table 5: City Sensors Locations

Description	Identification and location of the air quality and meteorology sensors	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	Web service	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	http://dados.cm-lisboa.pt/dataset/monitorizacao-de-parametros-ambientais-da-cidade-de-lisboa/resource/2c1c1286-78a2-4c58-91cb-776919ef9839	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	80 records (static)	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
locationId	identification number of the sensor box location	Number
address	address/name of the sensor box location	text

sensors	<p>type of parameters measured in the location following the next naming convention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicator (2 digits) ME - Meteorology QA - Air Quality RU - Noise CT - Traffic Counter - Parameter (4 digits) C6H6 - Benzene 00CO - Carbon Monoxide 00HR - Relative Humidity LAEQ - Equivalent continuous sound level, in dB(A) 0NO2 - Nitrogen Dioxide 00O3 - Ozone 00PA - Atmospheric Pressure PM10 - Particles with a diameter less than 10 µm PM2.5 - Particles with a diameter less than 2.5 µm 0SO2 - Sulfur Dioxide TEMP - Temperature 0VTH - Hourly Traffic Volume 00UV - Ultraviolet 00VD - Wind Direction 00VI - Wind Intensity - Location (4 digits) - referring to the identification number of the sensor box location (field name "locationId") 	string
coordinates	coordinates ("x", "y", "z", "lat" and "lng") of the sensor box location	Coordinates

Table 6: City Sensors Last Record

Description	Last record received for all parameters and all sensors locations (hourly data)	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	Web service	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	http://opendata-cml.qart.pt/lastmeasurements	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	427 records/hour (with the potential to increase to 500-700 records/hour in the coming months)	
Historical data	- (hourly data)	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type

id	<p>identification of the of parameters and sensor following the next naming convention:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicator (2 digits) ME - Meteorology QA - Air Quality RU - Noise CT - Traffic Counter - Parameter (4 digits) C6H6 - Benzene 00CO - Carbon Monoxide 00HR - Relative Humidity LAEQ - Equivalent continuous sound level, in dB(A) 0NO2 - Nitrogen Dioxide 00O3 - Ozone 00PA - Atmospheric Pressure PM10 - Particles with a diameter less than 10 µm PM2.5 - Particles with a diameter less than 2.5 µm 0SO2 - Sulfur Dioxide TEMP - Temperature 0VTH - Hourly Traffic Volume 00UV - Ultraviolet 00VD - Wind Direction 00VI - Wind Intensity - Location (4 digits) - referring to the identification number of the sensor box location 	text
avg	temporal basis of the measurement/record	text
date	date of the record	datetime
date standard	date naming standard	text
value	parameter value registered by the sensor	number
unit	units of the record/measurement	text
address	address/name of the sensor location	text
coordinates	coordinates ("x", "y", "z", "lat" and "lng") of the sensor measuring the parameter	coordinates

Table 7: City Sensors Historical data

Description	Historical data of the records measured for all parameters
Format	JSON
Protocol	Web service
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<p>Sample for the temperature recorded during June 24 on sensor with ID=1: http://opendata-cml.qart.pt/measurements/METEMP0001?startDate=202106240000&endDate=202106250000</p>

Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	427 records/hour starting from 24/05/2021	
Historical data	427 records/hour starting from 24/05/2021	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
id	identification of the of parameters and sensor following the next naming convention: - Indicator (2 digits) ME - Meteorology QA - Air Quality RU - Noise CT - Traffic Counter - Parameter (4 digits) C6H6 - Benzene 00CO - Carbon Monoxide 00HR - Relative Humidity LAEQ - Equivalent continuous sound level, in dB(A) 0NO2 - Nitrogen Dioxide 00O3 - Ozone 00PA - Atmospheric Pressure PM10 - Particles with a diameter less than 10 µm PM2.5 - Particles with a diameter less than 2.5 µm 0SO2 - Sulfur Dioxide TEMP - Temperature 0VTH - Hourly Traffic Volume 00UV - Ultraviolet 00VD - Wind Direction 00VI - Wind Intensity - Location (4 digits) - referring to the identification number of the sensor box location	text
avg	temporal basis of the measurement/record	text
date	date of the record	datetime
date standard	date naming standard	text
value	parameter value registered by the sensor	number
unit	units of the record/measurement	text

Table 8: Gree Structure

Description	Lisbon green structure	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	Web service	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	https://services.arcgis.com/1dSrZEWVQn5kHHyK/arcgis/rest/services/Ambiente_DMEVAE/FeatureServer/4/query?where=1%3D1&outFields=*&f=pgeojson	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	1000 records	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
type	type of record	text
id	identification number of the shape	number
geometry	list of sub-fields providing the shape geometry	text
type	type of the shape (polygon, multipolygon, etc.)	text
coordinates	coordinates of the shape	coordinates
properties	list of sub-fields providing the shape properties	text
objectid	shape ID	number
GIS Code (COD_SIG)	GIS code	number
Type ID (IDTIPO)	record date	number
SHAPE_LENG	?	number
Name (Nome)	name of the shape/record	text
Provider (Grupo)	shape/record provider	text
Address (Morada)	address of the shape/record	text
Owner (Gestao_121)	owner	text
Typology (Tipologia)	green shape typology	text
Area (Area_M2)	green space area	number
GlobalID	shape general ID	number
Shape_Area	shape area	number
Shape_Lenght	shape length	number

Table 9: Cycling Network

Description	Lisbon Cycling network
Format	GeoJSON
Protocol	Web service

Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	https://opendata.arcgis.com/datasets/440b7424a6284e0b9bf11179b95bf8d1_0.geojson	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	876 records	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
OBJECTID	record ID	number
RecordID (COD_VIA)	internal record ID	number
Design (DESIGNACAO)	list of sub-fields providing the shape geometry	text
Hierarchy (HIERARQUIA)	type of cycling route	text
Axis (EIXO)	-	-
Typology (TIPOLOGIA)	type of cycling route	text
Last Update (SITUACAO)	date of the last update	date
Parish (FREGUESIA)	name of the parish in which the cycling route is located	text
Project Name (NOME_PROJETO)	name of the project	text
Year (ANO)	year	number
Route Code (COD_CICLOVIA)	internal code of the cycling route	number
Integration Level (NIVEL_SEGREGACAO)	integration of the cycling route with the road network	text
Route Type (TIPO_INTERVENCAO)	type of cycling route	text
GlobalID	shape general ID	text
Shape__Length	cycling route shape area	number
geometry	list of sub-fields providing the shape geometry	text
paths	coordinates of the cycling route	coordinates

Table 10: Roads Network – main

Description	Lisbon main road network
Format	GeoJSON
Protocol	Web service
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	https://services.arcgis.com/1dSrZEWVQn5kHHyK/arcgis/rest/services/CartografiaBase/FeatureServer/1/query?where=1%3D1&outFields=*&f=pgeojson
Access restrictions	Open data
Volume	3763 records

Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
type	type of record	text
id	identification number of the record	number
geometry	list of sub-fields providing the shape geometry	text
type	type of the shape (polygon, multipolygon, string, etc.)	text
coordinates	coordinates of the shape	coordinates
properties	list of sub-fields providing the shape properties	text
objectid	shape ID	number
Shape Name (desig)	name of the shape/record	text
Hierarchy (hierarquia)	type of road	number
Hierarchy Level (nivel_hier)	type of road	number
Master Info (INFOPDM)	information from the master plan	text
GIS Code(COD_SIG)	GIS code of the record	number
Type ID (IDIDIPO)	identification number of the record	number
GlobalID	shape general ID	text
Shape_Lenght	record shape length	number

Table 11: Roads Network – secondary

Format	GeoJSON	
Protocol	Web service	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	https://services.arcgis.com/1dSrZEWVQn5kHHyK/arcgis/rest/services/Cultura_Toponimia/FeatureServer/0/query?where=1%3D1&outFields=*&f=geojson	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	3590 records	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Record Type (type)	type of record	text
id	identification number of the record	number
geometry	list of sub-fields providing the shape geometry	text
Shape Type (type)	type of the shape (polygon, multipolygon, string, etc.)	text

coordinates	coordinates of the shape	coordinates
properties	list of sub-fields providing the shape properties	text
objectid	shape ID	number
Shape Name (designacao)	name of the shape/record	text
legenda	-	-
Parish (freguesias)	name of the parish	text
Start (inicio)	road starting point	text
End (fim)	road finishing point	text
Theme (Temas)	theme for the name of the road	text
COD_LOCAL	local code	number
TOP_ID	road name ID	number
Shape_Lenght	record shape lenght	number

Table 12: Buildings & Demographics

Description	Data on the number and type of buildings and demographics	
Format	available in csv, dbf, prj, sbn, sbx, shp, shx or xml	
Protocol	file sharing	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	http://mapas.ine.pt/download/files/2011/municipios/BGRI2011_1106.zip	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	4736 records x 122 attributes	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
ano	year	number
geo_cod	geo code	number
geo_cod_dsg	name of the geo code	text
nivel	level of deaggregation	text
nivel_dsg	name of the deaggregation level	-
n_edificios_classicos	number of classic buildings	number
n_edificios_classicos_1ou2	number of classic buildings structurally built to have 1 or 2 flats	number
n_edificios_classicos_isolados	number of isolated classic buildings	number
n_edificios_classicos_gemin	number of classic semi-detached buildings	number
n_edificios_classicos_embanda	number of classic band buildings	number
n_edificios_classicos_3oumais	number of classic buildings structurally built to have 3 or more flats	number

D2.3 Definition and Specification of Policy-Related Datasets V1

n_edificios_classicos_outros	number of other classic building	number
n_edificios_exclusiv_resid	number of exclusively residential buildings	number
n_edificios_principal_resid	number of Mainly non-residential buildings	number
n_edificios_princip_ nao_resid	number of mainly residential buildings	number
n_edificios_1ou2_pisos	number of Buildings with 1 or 2 floors	number
n_edificios_3ou4_pisos	number of Buildings with 3 or 4 floors	number
n_edificios_5ou_mais_pisos	number of Buildings with 5 or more floors	number
n_edificios_constr_antes_1919	number of Buildings built before 1919	number
n_edificios_constr_1919a1945	number of Buildings built between 1919 and 1945	number
n_edificios_constr_1946a1960	number of Buildings built between 1946 and 1960	number
n_edificios_constr_1961a1970	number of Buildings built between 1961 and 1970	number
n_edificios_constr_1971a1980	number of Buildings built between 1971 and 1980	number
n_edificios_constr_1981a1990	number of Buildings built between 1981 and 1990	number
n_edificios_constr_1991a1995	number of Buildings built between 1991 and 1995	number
n_edificios_constr_1996a2000	number of Buildings built between 1996 and 2000	number
n_edificios_constr_2001a2005	number of Buildings built between 2001 and 2005	number
n_edificios_constr_2006a2011	number of Buildings built between 2006 and 2011	number
n_edificios_estrut_betao	number of Buildings with reinforced concrete structure	number
n_edificios_estrut_com_placa	number of Buildings with structure of masonry walls with plaque	number
n_edificios_estrut_sem_placa	number of Buildings with unmarked masonry wall structure	number
n_edificios_estrut_adobe_pedra	number of Buildings with adobe wall structure or loose stone masonry	number
n_edificios_estrut_outra	number of Buildings with another type of structure	number
n_alojamentos	total number of accomodations	number
n_alojamentos_familiares	number of family households	number
n_alojamentos_fam_classicos	number of classic family households	number
n_alojamentos_fam_n_classicos	number of non-classic family households	number
n_alojamentos_colectivos	number of colletive households	number
n_classicos_res_habitual	number of Classic housing for usual residence	number

D2.3 Definition and Specification of Policy-Related Datasets V1

n_alojamentos_res_habitual	number of family housing for usual residence	number
n_alojamentos_vagos	number of vacant family households	number
n_res_habitual_com_agua	number of households with water	number
n_res_habitual_com_retrete	number of households with toilet	number
n_res_habitual_com_esgotos	number of households with sewage	number
n_res_habitual_com_banho	number of households with bathtub	number
n_res_habitual_area_50	number of Classic family households with an area of up to 50 m2	number
n_res_habitual_area_50_100	number of Classic family households with an area of 50 to 100 m2	number
n_res_habitual_area_100_200	number of Classic family households with an area of 100 to 200 m2	number
n_res_habitual_area_200	number of Classic family households with an area higher than 200 m2	number
n_res_habitual_1_2_div	number of Classic family households of usual residence with 1 or 2 rooms	number
n_res_habitual_3_4_div	number of Classic family households of usual residence with 3 or 4 rooms	number
n_res_habitual_estac_1	number of Classic family households with parking for 1 vehicle	number
n_res_habitual_estac_2	number of Classic family households with parking for 2 vehicles	number
n_res_habitual_estac_3	number of Classic family households with parking for 3 or more vehicles	number
n_res_habitual_prop_ocup	number of Classic family households with owner-occupier	number
n_res_habitual_arrend	number of Classic family households for rented habitual residence	number
n_familias_classicas	total number of classic families	number
n_familias_institucionais	Total number of institutional families	number
n_familias_classicas_1ou2_pess	number of Classic families with 1 or 2 people	number
n_familias_classicas_3ou4_pess	number of Classic families with 3 or 4 people	number
n_familias_classicas_npes65	number of Classic families with people aged 65 and higher	number
n_familias_classicas_npes14	number of Classic families with people aged 15 and lower	number
n_familias_classic_sem_desemp	number of Classic families without unemployees	number
n_familias_classic_1desempreg	number of Classic families with 1 unemployee	number

D2.3 Definition and Specification of Policy-Related Datasets V1

n_familias_class_2mais_desemp	number of Classic families with more than 1 unemployee	number
n_nucleos_familiares	Total number of resident households	number
n_nucleos_1filh_nao_casado	number of families with 1 child not married	number
n_nucleos_2filh_nao_casado	number of families with 2 childs not married	number
n_nucleos_filh_inf_6anos	number of families with childs with less than 6 years old	number
n_nucleos_filh_inf_15anos	number of families with childs with less than 15 years old	number
n_nucleos_filh_mais_15anos	number of families with childs with less than 15 years old	number
n_individuos_present	Total number of persons	number
n_individuos_present_h	Total number of men	number
n_individuos_present_m	Total number of women	number
n_individuos_resident	total number of resident persons	number
n_individuos_resident_h	total number of resident men	number
n_individuos_resident_m	total number of resident women	number
n_individuos_resident_0a4	number of Residents aged between 0 and 4 years	number
n_individuos_resident_5a9	number of Residents aged between 5 and 9 years	number
n_individuos_resident_10a13	number of Residents aged between 10 and 13 years	number
n_individuos_resident_14a19	number of Residents aged between 14 and 19 years	number
n_individuos_resident_15a19	number of Residents aged between 15 and 19 years	number
n_individuos_resident_20a24	number of Residents aged between 20 and 24 years	number
n_individuos_resident_20a64	number of Residents aged between 20 and 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_25a64	number of Residents aged between 25 and 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_65	number of Residents aged higher than 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_0a4	number of men aged between 0 and 4 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_5a9	number of men aged between 5 and 9 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_10a13	number of men aged between 10 and 13 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_14a19	number of men aged between 14 and 19 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_15a19	number of men aged between 15 and 19 years	number

D2.3 Definition and Specification of Policy-Related Datasets V1

n_individuos_resident_h_20a24	number of men aged between 20 and 24 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_20a64	number of men aged between 20 and 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_25a64	number of men aged between 25 and 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_h_65	number of men aged higher than 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_0a4	number of women aged between 0 and 4 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_5a9	number of women aged between 5 and 9 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_10a13	number of women aged between 10 and 13 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_14a19	number of women aged between 14 and 19 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_15a19	number of women aged between 15 and 19 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_20a24	number of women aged between 20 and 24 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_20a64	number of women aged between 20 and 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_25a64	number of women aged between 25 and 64 years	number
n_individuos_resident_m_65	number of women aged higher than 64 years	number
n_indiv_resident_n_ler_escrv	number of Residents unable to read or write	number
n_ind_resident_fensino_1bas	number of residents attending the 1st cycle of basic education	number
n_ind_resident_fensino_2bas	number of residents attending the 2nd cycle of basic education	number
n_ind_resident_fensino_3bas	number of residents attending the 3rd cycle of basic education	number
n_ind_resident_fensino_sec	number of residents attending the secondary education	number
n_ind_resident_fensino_possec	number of residents attending post secondary education	number
n_ind_resident_fensino_sup	number of residents attending higher education	number
n_ind_resident_ensincomp_1bas	number of residents with the 1st cycle of basic education completed	number
n_ind_resident_ensincomp_2bas	number of residents with the 2nd cycle of basic education completed	number
n_ind_resident_ensincomp_3bas	number of residents with the 3rd cycle of basic education completed	number

n_ind_resident_ensincomp_sec	number of residents with the secondary education completed	number
n_ind_resident_ensincomp_posec	number of residents with the post secondary education completed	number
n_ind_resident_ensincomp_sup	number of residents with the higher education completed	number
n_ind_resid_desemp_proc_1emprg	number of Unemployed residents looking for 1st job	number
n_ind_resid_desemp_proc_emprg	number of unemployed resident looking for a new job	number
n_ind_resid_empregados	number of Residents employed	number
n_ind_resid_pens_reform	number of pensioner or retired residents	number
n_ind_resid_sem_act_econ	Indivíduos number of residents without economic activity	number
n_ind_resid_empreg_sect_prim	number of residents employed in the primary sector	number
n_ind_resid_empreg_sect_seq	number of residents employed in the secondary sector	number
n_ind_resid_empreg_sect_terc	number of residents employed in the tertiary sector	number
n_ind_resid_estud_mun_resid	number of residents studying in the municipality of residence	number
n_ind_resid_trab_mun_resid	number of residents working in the municipality of residence	number

Table 13: Meteo Reference Stations

Description	Weather Observation on Reference Stations (hourly data, last 24 hours). The dataset provides information on all existing stations in the country, so only the stations in Lisbon are of interest. These are the stations with the following IDs: "1200579"; "1210762"; "1200535"	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	Web Service	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	https://api.ipma.pt/open-data/observation/meteorology/stations/observations.json	
Access restrictions	Open Data	
Volume	576 records/day (72 entries/day x 8 parameters each)	
Historical data	last 24 hours	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
YYYY-mm-ddThh:mm	Date and hour of the record	date
StationID (idEstacao)	weather station identifier	number

Wind Intensity (intensidadeVentoKM)	wind intensity recorded at 10 meters high (km/h)	number
Temperature (temperatura)	air temperature recorded at 1.5 meters high, hourly average (°C)	number
Radiation (radiacao)	solar radiation (kJ/m2)	number
Wind Direction ID (idDireccVento)	wind direction class to the prevailing wind direction recorded at 10 meters high (0: without direction, 1 or 9: "N", 2: "NE", 3: "E", 4: "SE", 5: "S", 6: "SW", 7: "W", 8: "NW")	number
Accumulated Precipitation (precAcumulada)	precipitation recorded at a height of 1.5 meters, accumulated hourly value (mm)	number
Wind Intensity (intensidadeVento)	wind intensity recorded at 10 meters high (m/s)	number
Humidity (humidade)	relative air humidity recorded at 1.5 meters high, hourly average (%)	number
Pressure (pressao)	atmospheric pressure, reduced to mean sea level (NMM), hourly average (hPa)	number

Table 14: Meteo Reference Stations

Description	Weather Observation on Reference Stations (hourly data, last 24 hours). The dataset provides information on all existing stations in the country, so only the stations in Lisbon are of interest. These are the stations with the following IDs: "1200579"; "1210762"; "1200535"	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	file sharing	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	https://api.ipma.pt/open-data/observation/meteorology/stations/stations.json	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	3 records (static)	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
StationID (idEstacao)	identification number of the weather station	Number
StationName (localEstacao)	address/name of the weather station	text
geometry	list of sub-fields providing the shape geometry	string
type	type of the shape (polygon, multipolygon, etc.)	text
coordinates	coordinates ("lat" and "lng") of the weather station location	coordinates

Table 15: Meteo forecast

Description	Daily Weather Forecast up to 3 days, aggregated information per day
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Format	JSON	
Protocol	file sharing	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	http://api.ipma.pt/open-data/forecast/meteorology/cities/daily/1110600.json	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	3 records/day	
Historical data	forecast for next 3 days	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
owner	owner of the dataset	text
data	list of sub-fields providing forecast data	-
precipitaProb	rainfall probability (%)	number
tMin	daily minimum temperature	number
tMax	daily maximum temperature	number
predWindDir	predominant wind direction (N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW)	text
idWeatherType	weather type code	number
classWindSpeed	wind intensity class	number
longitude	longitude	coordinates
forecastDate	date for which the forecasted information is valid	date
classPreInt	rainfall intensity class	number
latitude	latitude	coordinates
globalIdLocal	location identifier	number
dataUpdate	file update date	date

Table 16: Weather class

Description	List of weather class identifiers. This is a subset enabling to interpret meteo forecast dataset
Format	JSON
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	https://api.ipma.pt/open-data/weather-type-classe.json
Access restrictions	Open data
Volume	27 records
Historical data	N/A
Anonymization	N/A

Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
owner	owner of the dataset	text
data	list of sub-fields providing the weather classes. "descWeatherTypeEN" option should be used to provide the description in english.	-
idWeatherType	weather classes identifier	number
descIdWeatherTypeEN	description of the weather class	text

Table 17: Rainfall Class

Description	List of rainfall class identifiers. This is a subset enabling to interpret meteo forecast dataset	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	file sharing	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	https://api.ipma.pt/open-data/precipitation-classe.json	
Access restrictions	Open data	
Volume	5 records	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
owner	owner of the dataset	text
data	list of sub-fields providing the rainfall classes. "descWeatherTypeEN" option should be used to provide the description in english.	-
classPreInt	rainfall class identifier	number
descClassPreIntEN	description of the rainfall class	text

Table 18: Wind Class

Description	List of wind class identifiers. This is a subset enabling to interpret meteo forecast dataset	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	file sharing	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	https://api.ipma.pt/open-data/wind-speed-daily-classe.json	
Access restrictions	Open data	

Volume	5 records	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
owner	owner of the dataset	text
data	list of sub-fields providing the wind classes. "descWeatherTypeEN" option should be used to provide the description in english.	-
classWindSpeed	wind class identifier	number
descClassWindSpeedDailyEN	description of the wind class	text

Table 19: Buildings Registry

Description	Identification and location of the building shapes in the city (building registry)	
Format	available in: cpg, dbf, prj, sbn, sbx, shp and shx	
Protocol	file sharing	
Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>	
Access restrictions	Permissions are being assessed with the dataset owner - the municipality.	
Volume	61981 records	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
idbuilding	identification number of the building	number
StationName (localEstacao)	address/name of the building station	text
geometry	list of sub-fields providing the shape geometry	string
type	type of the shape (polygon, multipolygon, etc.)	text
coordinates	coordinates ("lat" and "lng") of the weather station location	Coordinates

Table 20: Buildings data

Description	Dataset containing the characteristics of the buildings
Format	CSV
Protocol	file sharing

Protocol details	Endpoint	
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>	
Access restrictions	Permissions are being assessed with the dataset owner - the municipality.	
Volume	55569 records x 10 attributes	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
COD_SIG	identification number of the building	number
Classification Typology (CLASSIFICACAO_TIPOLOGIA)	classification of the building according to its type	text
Conservation State (ESTADO_CONSERVACAO)	conservation state of the building	text
Color (COR)	colour of the building façade	text
Property Regime (REGIME_PROPRIEDADE)	building property regime	text
Facade Cladding (REVESTIMENTO_FACHADA)	building facade cladding	text
Total Apartments (TOTAL_FRACCOES)	total number of apartments/flats	text
Total Floors (N_MAXIMO_PISOS)	total number of floors	text
Floors Under Ground (N_PISOS_ABAIXO_SOLO)	number of floors under ground level	text
Floors Above Ground (N_PISOS_ACIMA_SOLO)	number of floor above ground level	text

Table 21: Renewable Energy Systems (RES) Systems

Description	Identification of the renewable energy systems existing in the city
Format	CSV
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>
Access restrictions	public
Volume	2464 records
Historical data	- (update on a weekly basis)
Anonymization	N/A
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A

Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Data	system identification date	datetime
How (Como)	information on how the system has been identified	number
Internal System Number (Ordem)	internal number of the system	number
ObjectID/BGRI	identification number of the system	text
Status	type of renewable energy system	text
Address (Motrada/Zona)	address of the building in which the system is installed	text
Postal Code (Código Postal)	post code of the building in which the system is installed	text
District (ZONA)	district of the building in which the system is installed	text
Number of Systems (Observações)	number of systems installed	number
Coordinates (Coordenadas)	coordinates ("lat" and "lng") of the system	coordinates

Table 22: Solar Radiation (hourly)

Description	solar radiation map for the city of Lisbon (hourly timestep)
Format	TIFF
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>
Access restrictions	only for the purpose of the project
Volume	>25 TB
Historical data	N/A
Anonymization	N/A
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A

Table 23: Solar Radiation (yearly)

Description	solar radiation yearly cumulative map for the city of Lisbon
Format	TIFF
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>
Access restrictions	only for the purpose of the project
Volume	>3 GB
Historical data	N/A
Anonymization	N/A

Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A
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Table 24: Digital Surface Model (DSM)

Description	Lisbon digital surface model
Format	TIFF
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>
Access restrictions	only for the purpose of the project
Volume	>3 GB
Historical data	N/A
Anonymization	N/A
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A

Table 25: Slope and Orientation

Description	Slope and orientation of digital surface model (0.4m x 0.4m resolution)
Format	TIFF
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>
Access restrictions	only for the purpose of the project
Volume	>7 GB
Historical data	N/A
Anonymization	N/A
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A

Table 26: Building Footprint EC

Description	Energy consumption footprint of buildings
Format	CSV
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>
Access restrictions	Permissions are being assessed with the buildings' owners.
Volume	>200 records
Historical data	N/A
Anonymization	N/A

Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A
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Table 27: Energy consumption

Description	Energy consumption of the buildings for those having energy consumption (records every 15 minutes)
Format	CSV
Protocol	file sharing
Protocol details	Endpoint
Sample	<i>to be provided later</i>
Access restrictions	Permissions are being assessed with the buildings' owners.
Volume	> 20 000 records per day
Historical data	4 years
Anonymization	No
Security and Privacy Considerations	N/A

3.3 Citizens and Businesses Services Optimization (CDG)

Table 28: Accidents

Description	Data about accident collected from Verbatel Application	
Format	Microsoft Sqlserver rel. 2016	
Protocol	Sqlserver query port 1521	
Protocol details	Endpoints, credentials, etc	
Sample		
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	450 GB	
Historical data	> 10 years	
Anonymization	no	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential Data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Incident date	Date of claim	datetime
Day	Day of the week (Mon, Tue, Wed, Thu, Fri, Sat, Sun)	varchar
Accident time	Time of claim	datetime

Municipality	Municipality (Genoa)	varchar
1. Road	Road place of the accident	varchar
Sicom code	Reference code combined with the name of the road where the accident took place	varchar
2. Road	When filled in, identify the intersection or reference along the road	int
Sicom Code (2)	Reference code combined with the name of the intersection or reference road	varchar
Location type	Descriptive field indicating a locality or place reference	varchar
Latitude	Georeferenced coordinate	float
Longitude	Georeferenced coordinate	float
Town center	Confirmation of whether in built-up area or out of built-up area (yes, no)	varchar
Type of accident	Description of the type of accident	int
Road type	Indicates if urban road, state road within the inhabited center or other	int
Road characteristics	Description of the road (straight, curve, free view curve, traffic light intersection, underpass etc)	int
Road surface condition	Conditions of the road surface (dry, wet from rain, slippery from oily substances etc.)	int
Pavement type	Type of road surface (asphalt, dirt, etc.)	int
Weather conditions	Describes the weather conditions detected (Cloudy, rain in progress, clear etc.)	varchar
Traffic conditions	Traffic detected (low, normal, heavy etc.)	varchar
Property damage	Damage to artifacts or street furniture (yes, no)	varchar
Accident with injuries	People with injuries (yes, no)	varchar
Injured persons	Total number of people injured	int
Injured pedestrians	Number of pedestrians injured	int
Fatalities	Total number of people killed	int
Pedestrian fatalities	Number of pedestrians killed	int
Prognosis reserved	Number of people in a reserved prognosis	int

Prognosis up to 20 days	Number of persons with a prognosis of up to 20 days	int
Prognosis from 21 to 40 days	Number of persons with a prognosis between 21 and 40 days	int
Prognosis over 40 days	Number of persons with a prognosis of more than 40 days	int
Vehicles involved	Total vehicles involved	int
Car pr.	Number of cars for private use involved	int
Passenger car pb.	Number of cars for public use involved	int
Truck	Number of trucks involved	int
Bus	Number of buses involved	int
Motorcycle	Number of motorcycles involved	int
Motorcycle	Number of motorcycles involved	int
Moped	Number of mopeds involved	int
Quadricycle	Number of quadricycles involved	int
Velocipede	Number of velocipedes involved	int
Electric micromobility	Number of alternative means for electric mobility	int
Other	Number of other vehicles or vehicles that cannot be classified	int
Violations	Violations ascertained in the accident detection	int
Age	Age of persons involved (when indicated)	int
Blood alcohol level	When present, indicates the blood alcohol level of the drivers involved	int

Table 29: Meteo data

Description	Meteo Data collected by several data logger installed on Genova municipality territory
Format	Mysql Database
Protocol	Mysql clienet
Protocol details	Endpoints, credentials, etc
Sample	Put a link to a file with a sample of the data source (e.g. a JSON file, a CSV file etc). The sample should follow the same format that will be used during data exchange.

Access restrictions	Proprietary or Open Data or other access restrictions	
Volume	7 GB	
Historical data	24 month	
Anonymization	Not applicable	
Security and Privacy Considerations	State here if the data processors should be aware of any security and privacy considerations. Should we treat the data as confidential? NO	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
IDS	Datalogger Identifier	Integer
IdStation	Datalogger description (i.e. pontedecimo, voltri pra, etc)	Varchar
Dataora	Date and time of detection	Datetime
W_att	Wind speed (current)	Float
W_raf	Wind speed (gust)	Float
W_dir	Wind direction (NE, ENE, NNW, etc)	Varchar
T_Att	Current temperature	Float
H_att	current humidity	Float
P_att		Float
R_Day	Rain on day	Float
R_Month	rain in month	Float
r_year	rain in year	Float
r_att	current rain	Float
R_Max	rain (maximum peak)	Float
T_Int	Inside temperature	Integer
H_Int	indoor humidity	Integer
HH	hour of detection	Integer
MM	minute of detection	Integer
WC_ATT	Temperature	Float
T_MAXDAY	Maximum temperature during the day	Float

T_MINDAY	Minimum temperature during the day	Float
W_MAX	Wind speed max	Float
DP_ATT		Float
W_MAXAVG	Wind speed max average	Float
W_ATT10	Wind speed	Float
W_DIRG	Wind direction	Float

Table 30: AMT Stops

Description	Data set on the AMT (Azienda Mobilità e Trasporti - company holding the concession for public transport) Collection mechanism: manual	
Format	CSV	
Protocol	FTP	
Protocol details	Web server directory	
Sample	Yes	
Access restrictions	NO	
Volume	365 records	
Historical data	N/A	
Anonymization	No	
Security and Privacy Considerations	public data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Stop_id	Bus stop id	String
stop_name	Bus stop name	String
stop_desc	Equal to Bus stop id	String
stop_lat	Bus stop coordinate, latitude	number
stop_lon	Bus stop coordinate, longitude	number
Stop_id	Bus stop id	String

Table 31: Post

Description	Data set on reports/posts submitted by citizens on the “SegnalaCi” application. Collection mechanism: via API	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	API REST	
Protocol details	API available	
Sample	Post - Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	number of records: 20210	
Historical data	8 months (since January 2021)	
Anonymization	No	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
id	Unique identifier	number
uuid	Universal unique identifier	string
published_at	Publication date	string (\$date-time)
modified_at	Last modification date	string (\$date-time)
expiry_at	Expiration date	string (\$date-time)
closed_at	Closing date	string (\$date-time)
subject	Subject	string
description	description	string
address	address	string
longitude	longitude	number
latitude	latitude	number
type	type (report, suggestion, claim)	string
status	status (pending, open, close)	string
privacy_status	Privacy status (public, private)	string
moderation_status	Moderation status (waiting, approved)	string
author	author	integer
reporter	Reporter	integer
image	Image (first post image)	string (\$url)
images	Images	string (\$url)
is_comments_allowed	Comments allowed	boolean
channel	Channel (ohone, Mail or fax, E-mail, office)	string

Table 32: Category

Field name	Field description	Field type
id	Unique identifier	number
name	Name	string

parent	Parent category id	number
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Table 33: User

Description	Data set on the users submitting the report on the “SegnalaCi” platform Collection mechanism: via API	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	API REST	
Protocol details	API available	
Sample	User - Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	number of records: 20210	
Historical data	8 months (since January 2021)	
Anonymization	No	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
id	Unique identifier	number
type	User type	string
groups	User group	integer

Table 34: Group

Description	Data set on Departments or Unit offices in charge of managing reports. Collection mechanism: via API	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	API REST	
Protocol details	API available	
Sample	Group - Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	number of records: 20210	
Historical data	8 months (since January 2021)	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
id	Unique identifier	number
name	Name	string
email	Group email	string

Table 35: Type

Description	Data set on the type of the post (report, suggestion, claim). Collection mechanism: via API	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	API REST	
Protocol details	API available	
Sample	Type - Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	number of records: 20210	
Historical data	8 months (since January 2021)	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
id	Unique identifier	number
name	Name	string

Table 36: Facility Management Database

Description	This dataset contains all the extraordinary maintenance interventions achieved from Facility Management Direction of the Municipality of Genoa	
Format	XLS	
Protocol	File sharing	
Protocol details	Used by Facility Management Direction	
Sample	Database Direzione Facility Management	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	Mb	
Historical data	3 years	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Exclusive use of Facility Management Direction	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Typology (Tipology)	Type of contract used	Text
MOGE	Number of the contract in MOGE database	Text
Object	The item object of extraordinary maintenance	Text
Problem	The trouble to be solved with extraordinary maintenance	Text
Address	The location address of the item	Text
Neighborhood	The neighborhood where the item is	Text
Amount	The amount of the extraordinary maintenance	Number
Type of building	The type of building object of extraordinary maintenance	Text
State	The progress of building works	Text

Start	The date of start	Datetime
End	The date of end	Datetime

3.4 Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance Policies (BURGAS)

Table 37: Measurement Location

Description	This dataset contains information about the water pipes that will be turned into smart pipes.	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, Web service	
Protocol details	File exports available on demand	
Sample	Measurement Location Data Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	30 000 records	
Historical data	3 years	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Data is not confidential	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
ID	The ID of the point of measurement	Unique Number
Address	The address of the point of measurement	Text
Location latitude	The latitude of the point of measurement	Coordinates
Location longitude	The longitude of the point of measurement	Coordinates

Table 38: Smart Pipes

Description	This dataset contains information about the water pipes that will be turned into smart pipes.	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, Web service	
Protocol details	File exports available on demand	
Sample	Smart Pipes Data Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	30 000 records	
Historical data	3 years	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Data is not confidential	

Field name	Field description	Field type
Address	The address of the point of measurement	Text = Address of Measurement Location
Diameter	The diameter of the water pipe in millimeters	Number

Material	The material of the water pipe	Text (needs to be able to be encoded in cyrillic scripts as well)
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Table 39: Accidents, Metered Water and Water Losses

Description	This dataset contains the results that will be used in data analysis and statistics	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, Web service	
Protocol details	File exports available on demand	
Sample	Accidents, MW and Water Losses Data Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	100 000 records	
Historical data	3 years	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Data is not confidential	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Address	The address of the point of measurement	Text
Start Date	The start date of the measurement	Date
End Date	The end date of the measurement	Date
Accidents	The number of accidents (pipe bursts) for the time period	Number
Metered water	The water used in households or companies that is measured by their water meters (legal water consumption) in cubic meters for the time period	Number
Water losses	The amount of water (in %) that is lost (water leaks, pipe bursts, illegal connections or metering errors) for the time period	Percentages
Cost of Repair	The total cost of repairworks for the period in BGN for the time period	number
Total Water losses	The total amount of water lost in liters	number
Age of pipes	Age of existing pipe infrastrucure in years	number

Table 40: Measurements

Description	This dataset contains the measurements done by the smart pipes.	
Format	CSV, JSON	
Protocol	File sharing, Web service	
Protocol details	File exports available on demand	
Sample	Measurements Data Sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	600 000 records	
Historical data	3 years	
Anonymization	N/A	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Data is not confidential	
Data Fields/Model		

Field name	Field description	Field type
Address	The address of the point of measurement	Text
Date	The date and the time of the measurement	Datetime
Water Flow rate	The amount of water (in liters) that passes through the pipe per second	Number
Water Pressure	The water pressure in bars	Number
Water Velocity	The water velocity in meters per second	Number
Water temperature	The temperature of the water	Number

3.5 Holistic and Accessible Urban Mobility (NIC)

Table 41: Nicosia Buses - Calendar CPT

Description	Data Archive General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) (Attitudes, Program, Routes), which are updated at regular intervals and when needed	
Format	CSV, GTFS-RT	
Protocol	File sharing, web service and cloud services	
Protocol details	Open API (REST, HTTPS, JASON, MQTT, Websockets), GSM, Sigfox and NB-IoT	
Sample	https://www.data.gov.cy/node/4020?language=en	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	365 rows for 1 year	
Historical data	From March 2017 until January 2022 (59 months)	
Anonymization	Static	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Open data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
route_id	Identifies a route.	ID referencing routes.route_id
service_id	Identifies a set of dates when service is available for one or more routes.	ID referencing calendar.service_id or calendar_dates.service_id
trip_id	Identifies a trip..	ID
trip_headsign	Text that appears on signage identifying the trip's destination to riders.	Text
shape_id	Identifies a geospatial shape describing the vehicle travel path for a trip.	ID referencing shapes.shape_id
direction_id	Indicates the direction of travel for a trip. This field is not used in routing; it provides a way to separate trips by direction when publishing time tables. Valid options are: 0 - Travel in one direction (e.g. outbound travel). 1 - Travel in the opposite direction (e.g. inbound travel).	Enum
route_id	Identifies a route.	ID referencing routes.route_id
service_id	Identifies a set of dates when service is available for one or more routes.	ID referencing calendar.service_id or calendar_dates.service_id
trip_id	Identifies a trip..	ID

Table 42: Nicosia Buses - TRIPS CPT

Description	Traffic analysis. Data collected from the cameras	
Format	JSON/ xlsx	
Protocol	MQTT, CoAP or HTTP protocols	
Protocol details	Open API(REST,HTTPS,JASON,MQTT,Websockets) ,GSM,Sigfox and NB-IoT	
Sample	Traffic Analysis Data	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	Update every one hour	
Historical data	3-5 months	
Anonymization	The data are anonymized	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Non confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
route_id	Identifies a route.	ID referencing routes.route_id
service_id	Identifies a set of dates when service is available for one or more routes.	ID referencing calendar.service_id or calendar_dates.service.id
trip_id	Identifies a trip..	ID
trip_headsign	Text that appears on signage identifying the trip's destination to riders.	Text
shape_id	Identifies a geospatial shape describing the vehicle travel path for a trip.	ID referencing shapes.shape_id
direction_id	Indicates the direction of travel for a trip. This field is not used in routing; it provides a way to separate trips by direction when publishing time tables. Valid options are: 0 - Travel in one direction (e.g. outbound travel). 1 - Travel in the opposite direction (e.g. inbound travel).	Enum

Table 43: Nicosia Buses - STOPS CPT

Description	Data Archive General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) (Attitudes, Program, Routes), which are updated at regular intervals and when needed.	
Format	CSV, GTFS-RT	
Protocol	File sharing, web service and cloud services	
Protocol details	Open API(REST,HTTPS,JASON,MQTT,Websockets) ,GSM,Sigfox and NB-IoT	
Sample	https://www.data.gov.cy/node/4020?language=en	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	250 Rows	
Historical data	Static	
Anonymization		
Security and Privacy Considerations	Open data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type

stop_id	Identifies a stop, station, or station entrance. The term "station entrance" refers to both station entrances and station exits. Stops, stations or station entrances are collectively referred to as locations. Multiple routes may use the same stop.	ID
stop_code	Short text or a number that identifies the location for riders.	Text
stop_name	Name of the location. Use a name that people will understand in the local and tourist vernacular.	Text
stop_desc	This field is used to specify the short name of the stop..	Text
stop_lat	Latitude of the location. The coordinates must be the ones of the bus pole — if exists — and otherwise of where the travelers are boarding the vehicle (on the sidewalk or the platform, and not on the roadway or the track where the vehicle stops).	Latitude
stop_lon	Longitude of the location. The coordinates must be the ones of the bus pole — if exists — and otherwise of where the travelers are boarding the vehicle (on the sidewalk or the platform, and not on the roadway or the track where the vehicle stops).	Longitude

Table 44: Nicosia Buses ROUTES – CPT

Description	Data Archive General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) (Attitudes, Program, Routes), which are updated at regular intervals and when needed.	
Format	CSV, GTFS-RT	
Protocol	File sharing, web service and cloud services	
Protocol details	Open API(REST,HTTPS,JASON,MQTT,Websockets) ,GSM,Sigfox and NB-IoT	
Sample	https://www.data.gov.cy/node/4020?language=en	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	250 Rows	
Historical data	Static	
Anonymization		
Security and Privacy Considerations	Open data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
route_id	Identifies a route.	id: "number"
agency_id	Agency for the specified route. This field is required when the dataset provides data for routes from more than one agency in agency.txt, otherwise it is optional.	ID referencing agency.agency_id
route_short_name	Short name of a route. This will often be a short, abstract identifier like "32", "100X", or "Green" that riders use to identify a route, but which doesn't give any indication of what places the route serves. Either route_short_name or route_long_name must be specified, or potentially both if appropriate.	Text
route_long_name	Full name of a route. This name is generally more descriptive than the route_short_name and often includes the route's destination or stop. Either	Text

	route_short_name or route_long_name must be specified, or potentially both if appropriate.	
route_desc	Description of a route that provides useful, quality information.	Text
route_type	Indicates the type of transportation used on a route. Valid options are: 0 - Tram, Streetcar, Light rail. Any light rail or street level system within a metropolitan area. 1 - Subway, Metro. Any underground rail system within a metropolitan area. 2 - Rail. Used for intercity or long-distance travel. 3 - Bus. Used for short- and long-distance bus routes. 4 - Ferry. Used for short- and long-distance boat service. 5 - Cable car. Used for street-level cable cars where the cable runs beneath the car. 6 - Gondola, Suspended cable car. Typically used for aerial cable cars where the car is suspended from the cable. 7 - Funicular. Any rail system designed for steep inclines.	Enum
route_color	Route color designation that matches public facing material. Defaults to white (FFFFFF) when omitted or left empty. The color difference between route_color and route_text_color should provide sufficient contrast when viewed on a black and white screen.	Color
route_text_color	Legible color to use for text drawn against a background of route_color. Defaults to black (000000) when omitted or left empty. The color difference between route_color and route_text_color should provide sufficient contrast when viewed on a black and white screen.	Color

Table 45: Smart Parking Management

Description	Enhancing sustainable, urban mobility by means of technological means (Parking Data per sensor)	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	MQTT, CoAP or HTTP protocols	
Protocol details	Open API(REST,HTTPS,JASON,MQTT,Websockets) ,GSM,Sigfox and NB-IoT	
Sample	Smart Parking Management Data	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	Can not specified	
Historical data	3-5 months	
Anonymization	The data are anonymized	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Non confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Asset Name	District / area	String
Device ID	The id of parking sensor	id: "number"
Device Name	The name of parking sensor	name:"string"

Last Active Date	The last date that the parking sensor was alive	Date and Time
Vacant/occupied	Status of parking sensor	Specific values
Status	Shows the status of the parking sensor	String - Specific values

Table 46: Monitoring Environmental

Description	Measurements on an hourly basis with six environmental sensors and dynamic information of the citizens throughout the Municipality	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	MQTT, CoAP or HTTP protocols	
Protocol details	Open API(REST,HTTPS,JASON,MQTT,Websockets) ,GSM,Sigfox and NB-IoT	
Sample	Monitoring Environmental Data	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	Update every one hour	
Historical data	3-5 months	
Anonymization	The data are anonymized	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Non confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Asset Name	District / area	String
Device ID	The id of parking sensor	id: "number"
Device Name	The name of parking sensor	name:"string"
Last Active Date	The last date that the parking sensor was alive	Date and Time
Air Quality Index	the value of the Airquality index	Number
Air Quality Rating	the rating of the air quality index (good/ fair/ moderate / poor / very poor / extremely poor)	String - Specific values
Status	Shows the status of the parking sensor	String - Specific values

Table 47: Traffic Analysis

Description	Traffic analysis. Data collected from the cameras	
Format	JSON/ xlsx	
Protocol	MQTT, CoAP or HTTP protocols	
Protocol details	Open API(REST,HTTPS,JASON,MQTT,Websockets) ,GSM,Sigfox and NB-IoT	
Sample	Traffic Analysis Data	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	Update every one hour	
Historical data	3-5 months	

Anonymization	The data are anonymized	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Non confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Date	Date of the value	Date
Camera	Camera ID	Number
Line	Line ID	Number
People	Counter of People	Number
Bicycles	Counter of Bicycles	Number
Cars	Counter of Cars	Number
Motorcycles	Counter of Motorcycles	Number
Buses	Counter of Buses	Number
Trucks	Counter of Trucks	Number
Total	Total number of counting objects	Number

Table 48: SPL Sensor

Description	This dataset represents the UNPARALLEL Noise Sensor in the UNPARALLEL Infrastructure	
Format	JSON	
Protocol	Grafana Data source API	
Protocol details	https://grafana.com/docs/grafana/latest/developers/http_api/data_source/	
Sample	Put a link to a file with a sample of the data source (e.g. a JSON file, a CSV file etc). The sample should follow the same format that will be used during data exchange.	
Access restrictions	ACL Based, depends on the location of the device	
Volume	86400 records per day (one reading per second)	
Historical data	Unlimited (Constraint on the disk sizes)	
Anonymization	Readings doesn't have the location, it is associated with the device, one can choose to share the device location or not	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Privacy is achieved at the device level, if the device details is shared or not, not included in this dataset.	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
LAeq (1 sec)	Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the last second	LAeq (1 sec)
LAeq (30 sec)	Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the last 30 seconds	LAeq (30 sec)
LAeq (1 min)	Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the last minute	LAeq (1 min)
LAeq (15 min)	Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the last 15 minutes	LAeq (15 min)
LA_day	Sound Exposure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) from 07:00 upt to 19:00 (the start and stop time can be configured, depending on the local requirement)	LA_day
LA_evening	Sound Exposure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) from 19:00 upt to 23:00 (the start and stop time can be configured, depending on the local requirement)	LA_evening

LA_night	Sound Exposure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) from 23:00 up to 07:00 (the start and stop time can be configured, depending on the local requirement)	LA_night
LA_den	Sound Exposure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) based on LA_day, LA_evening and LA_night according to the directive 2002/49/CE	LA_den
LAeq	Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of a defined period	LAeq
LAmx	Maximum value of Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) occurred in a defined period	LAmx
LAmn	Minimum value of Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) occurred in a defined period	LAmn
LA1	Percentil based on LAeq_dt of the level that was exceeded for 1% of the defined period	LA1
LA10	Percentil based on LAeq_dt of the level that was exceeded for 10% of the defined period	LA10
LA50	Percentil based on LAeq_dt of the level that was exceeded for 50% of the defined period	LA50
LA90	Percentil based on LAeq_dt of the level that was exceeded for 90% of the defined period	LA90
LA99	Percentil based on LAeq_dt of the level that was exceeded for 99% of the defined period	LA99
LAS	Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the Slow measurement of time weighting (1 second time constant)	LAS
LAF	Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the Fast measurement of time weighting (0.125 second time constant)	LAF
LASmax	Maximum value of the Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the Slow measurement of time weighting since the start of the measurements	LASmax
LASmin	Minimum value of the Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the Slow measurement of time weighting since the start of the measurements	LASmin
LAFmax	Maximum value of the Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the Fast measurement of time weighting since the start of the measurements	LAFmax
LAFmin	Minimum value of the Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of the Fast measurement of time weighting since the start of the measurements	LAFmin
LAeq (15 min max)	The maximum occurred in the day (or since the beginning of the measurement until the request) of the Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of 15 minutes	LAeq (15 min max)
LAeq (30 min max)	The maximum occurred in the day (or since the beginning of the measurement until the request) of the Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of 30 minutes	LAeq (30 min max)
LAeq (1 hour max)	The maximum occurred in the day (or since the beginning of the measurement until the request) of the Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of 1 hour	LAeq (1 hour max)
LAeq (2 hour max)	The maximum occurred in the day (or since the beginning of the measurement until the request) of the Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of 2 hours	LAeq (2 hour max)
LAeq (4 hour max)	The maximum occurred in the day (or since the beginning of the measurement until the request) of the Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of 4 hours	LAeq (4 hour max)
LAeq (8 hour max)	The maximum occurred in the day (or since the beginning of the measurement until the request) of the Equivalent Continuous Sound Pressure Level in dBA (A-weighting frequency) of 8 hours	LAeq (8 hour max)

Filter_selection	All the measurements are according to the A or C-weighting frequency response	Filter_selection
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Table 49: Patrol Reports

Description	Patrols reports. Patrols take place in different areas of Nicosia Municipality limits by an acoustician, especially in the city centre. The purpose is to monitor and assess the levels of the music / sound that escapes from entertainment establishments and implement preventive actions in order to improve the acoustic environment of the city.	
Format	CSV	
Protocol	File sharing, Web service	
Protocol details	HTTP, files with excel tables available on demand	
Sample	Patrol report sample	
Access restrictions	Proprietary	
Volume	approximately 67 reports (mean:12 lines each report = total 804 lines)	
Historical data	From March 2017 until January 2022 (59 months)	
Anonymization	Anonymized data, refer only the name of the street	
Security and Privacy Considerations	Confidential data	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Creation date	The creation date of the patrol	Date
Day	The day of the week that the patrol took place	Text / day
Address	Name of the street where measured noise levels	Text
Background noise	Noise of the area where the entertainment establishment is (it not includes any noise produced from the defined entertainment establishment)	Number (dB)
Total noise level	Total noise level 3m distance from a specific entertainment establishment	Number (dB)
Time	The time that the measures for a specific entertainment establishment took place (time in Cyprus)	Number (hour/minutes)
Colour	The colour describes the result or the problem	Red - serious problem, Yellow – medium problem, Green – within the acceptable limits/no problem.
Comments	Thoughts, recommendations and observations of acoustician.	Text

4 Dataset Model Design

The following diagram shows the UML model built from the data collected from the data sources provided by the pilots.

To start we identified the common entities among the different domains available, this process involved a first screening of the data, trying to identify the fields in common between the different data sets. Once we created this temporary data structure, we tried to identify the new entities that could enclose the new data sets in common and we built a relational schema. We then included in the dataset also the specific data of each dataset divided according to the original entities.

This is a conceptual data model so it does not contain a granular description of every entity. The goal of this UML diagram is to capture a structural commonality of the datasets that we have and to provide a high-level view on the data.

Next stage would be to build a logic data model which will contain all granulars of the data and eventually will be used to design a corresponding DB schema. Logical model will also have operational and transactional data. For example, if we receive a new dataset which contains an update to the event that we already have, we need to store it in a way that no data is lost and the full history of the event is available.

Each color represents a different domain (pilot project). It also contains a common domain (blue color). It represents fundamental entities that are common for all pilots: Event, Location, Timeline, Status, Transaction, Payment. Relations between models are displayed, there are two types of them:

1. Line connection: it represents a relation between two entities and also specifies the cardinality (one-to-one, one-to-many). When the cardinality is not present on the line, it should be interpreted as a one-to-one relation.
2. Arrow connection: it represents an "is" relation between two entities.

Figure 2: AI4PublicPolicy Data Model

5 Policy Model Design

Leveraging on the CRISP-DM methodology and considering the Policy as an AI problem, we designed the Policy Model as a set of attributes and related entities that represents:

- Problem understanding
- Data understanding
- AI modelling
- AI outcomes

Following this methodology we designed the following entities that contain the necessary information to manage the Policy along the whole policy making process:

- Policy
- Dataset
- AI Model
- AI Workflow

A Policy represents an optimization problem and we can use different AI Algorithm to solve the problem and obtain multiple AI models providing recommendations and insights. Dataset object defines the available data related to the policy. AI Workflows are pipelines created to build the AI Models starting from the Dataset and the selected AI Algorithms. Two main UML diagrams are reported below to describe all this Entities.

5.1 Policy

The Policy entity includes name, description, objective, owner and status of the Policy. Linked to this entity we have a list of KPI with name and value and some metadata reporting version and category.

The we have a list of related Datasets with name, source, source type, description, owner and a list of all fields composing the datasets that could be used as an input to the AI algorithm.

Figure 3: AI4PublicPolicy Policy Model

5.2 AI Model

This entity is the result of the training of the AI Algorithm through the Datasets. It includes name, description, used AI Algorithm, identifier of the Workflow used to train the Algorithm, reference to the artifact representing the operational AI Model.

This entity is linked to

1. The list of learned parameters, specific for the selected AI Algorithm, with information on name, type and value
2. The domain model of the specific policy, reporting the input to provide to the model and the output provided by the model, i.e the recommendations of the AI model for the specific domain;

Figure 4: AI4PublicPolicy AI Model

This models will be used to design the objects saved within the platform and used by the components of the VPME.

6 Conclusions

This document presented two different studies:

- the analysis of the datasets from different Pilot's data sources in order to design a common data model.
- the study and design of the analytical model of a Policy as structural representations that will be enriched through the outcomes of the AI algorithms along the policy making process

The Dataset and Policy models reported in this deliverable will be the basis for the next technical analysis and an input for the following deliverables:

- D1.10 Data Management Plan
- D2.6 Conceptual model and Reference Architecture V1
- D3.1 Data Management and APIs for Data Collection V1

Annexes

Annex 1: Template for collecting data sources from Pilots

Description	A description of the data set, its usage and collection mechanisms	
Format	CSV, TSV, JSON, XML, JPG, MP3, etc	
Protocol	The protocol used to access the data (FTP, File sharing, Web service)	
Protocol details	Endpoints, credentials, etc	
Sample	Put a link to a file with a sample of the data source (e.g. a JSON file, a CSV file etc). The sample should follow the same format that will be used during data exchange.	
Access restrictions	Proprietary or Open Data or other access restrictions	
Volume	Size of the dataset in number of records or GBs	
Historical data	The period of historical data in months	
Anonymization	Have you applied any kind of anonymization of the provided data?	
Security and Privacy Considerations	State here if the data processors should be aware of any security and privacy considerations. Should we treat the data as confidential?	
Data Fields/Model		
Field name	Field description	Field type
Field 1	A detailed description of the field	Number, String, Text, Datetime, Co-ordinates, image, video, link to another data set record etc
Field 2